

Looking at depth: Shaping root systems for resource-efficient crops

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Resilient and sustainable crop production depends, among other things, on smart uptake of water and soil nutrients by crop root systems. Scientists have accumulated evidence that tailored root systems reaching deep soil layers will help reduce environmental impacts and improve resilience to climate change. Exploring these new paths starts with root system observation and investigation, which requires very specific and complimentary instrumented facilities. Continued supportive policy is therefore needed to amplify our root research capacity and commit it to support the agroecological transition.

Introduction

Water and nutrients are essential inputs to crop production. While water is primarily transpired in massive amounts (up to 500 gr of water for 1 gr of biomass produced), nutrients are constituents of the crop biomass and are used by plants for critical functions such as photosynthesis. Any factor or condition which reduces the availability of these nutrients (e.g., drought, disease, etc) limits the potential yield of the crop. In many areas in the world, this has led to an excess use of fertilizers that has largely contributed to going beyond planetary boundaries. In addition, climate change increases the frequency of water shortage episodes which affect crop growth negatively.

The root system of crops circumscribes the volume of the soil from which plants can take up their resources. Deep rooting is important for the uptake of soil resources at depth. Water and nitrogen are generally supplied in the topsoil by rainfall, irrigation, fertilizers and organic matter decomposition. If they are not absorbed fast enough from the topsoil, they move down into deeper soil layers, potentially beyond the root uptake domain. Crops equipped with deep roots can use these deep resources more effectively. They suffer less from episodes of water shortage and can reduce the losses of nitrogen

to the groundwater, which makes them more adapted to future climate change and more environmentally sustainable. Other nutrients, such as phosphorus and potassium, do not move as easily in the soil, but are abundant in the subsoil in many regions of Europe. Deep rooted crops can access these untapped resources and reduce the massive fertilizer imports on which EU agriculture is so dependent. In addition to this, deep rooting means extra biomass in the subsoil, which contributes to carbon (C) sequestration and climate change mitigation. Developing crops with enhanced capacity to grow extensive and deep root systems is therefore a serious option for breeders and farmers to face and mitigate climate change effects on crops while reducing environmental impacts of intensive crop production.

Deeper rooting can be achieved by soil and crop management, supported by optimized crop rotation to improve root growth and health and by genetics to increase deep rooting capacity. Generating impact with these options relies, however, on intensive studies and observation of root systems, for example root phenotyping. The SolACE project has used unique phenotyping facilities to analyse the genetic variability of root growth and architecture in potato and wheat.

Approach

Several SolACE partners were engaged in the phenotyping of wheat and potato genetic resources provided by breeders and geneticists. Complementary expertise allowed us to address different objectives. On the one side, it was important to observe large collections of varieties that geneticists rely on to elaborate breeding strategies. This was done in artificial conditions and on young plants, which is the only possible approach to handle large numbers of plants. On the other side, it was necessary to inform breeders about ideal phenotypes they should try to achieve in their programmes. To do this, observations were made on roots and yield in the field and during the whole crop cycle, to identify root features that lead to good agronomic performance under conditions where plants rely on well-developed root systems to capture soil resources. Because SolACE partners obtained root data under different conditions on the same genetic resources, they were also in an excellent position to evaluate the possibility of predicting the effect of new root phenotypes on field performance in future environmental conditions, using new crop simulation models developed in the project.

Key findings

Experiments in artificial phenotyping platforms (RootPhAir, UCLouvain / 4PMI, INRAE) revealed the existence of a large genetic diversity for root system architecture and for detailed root growth and developmental processes. The genetic analysis indicated that these features are heritable (up to 80 % for some of them), which indicates that creating new varieties with desired root features is within the reach of breeders. However, their genetic architecture was shown to be complex, so that modern genomic selection tools may be needed to advance selection sufficiently fast.

Experiments in semi-field facilities (RadiMax, University of Copenhagen / Rhizotrons, ARVALIS / Shovelomics, INRAE) validated the genetic diversity observed in artificial conditions. In addition, the RadiMax experiments further demonstrated that the different root architectures were linked with different abilities to extract water and nitrogen and, in particular, that deep roots were active in extracting soil resources in the deep soil layers and were reducing drought stress indicators. These results make deep roots a viable breeding target for environments where deep soil layers are accessible to roots.

What to do next?

The results obtained demonstrate that some root features are potential targets for breeding and suggest paths for improvement by means of genomic selection methods. There are, however, many genotypes to be evaluated in a considerable number of future environmental scenarios before we can confidently ensure that well defined root features or behaviour will confer higher agronomical performance in low-input and water deficit conditions. This exceeds by far the current capacity of field phenotyping installations. Innovation in low-cost, high throughput field phenotyping methods should therefore become a priority in the future, as well as the connection between phenotyping installations and a new generation of crop growth models that are able to integrate root phenotyping data in yield simulations. It is also important to raise the awareness of the importance of root traits, to encourage breeders to include them in their breeding targets and farmers to optimize their crop rotation and management.

Implications and recommendations

The phenotyping facilities involved in SolACE are part of the ESFRI-EMPHASIS¹ initiative, in which more than 20 EU countries have shown interest. The EMPHASIS portfolio of activities includes the priorities that have been pointed by SolACE partners. National and EU support for EMPHASIS and other research infrastructure (Table 1) will make sure that technical innovation in phenotyping goes on in a concerted way at the EU scale and allows the scientific and breeding communities to stand the difficult challenges ahead of current agriculture.

1 ESFRI is the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures. EMPHASIS is the European Infrastructure for Multi-scale Plant Phenomics and Simulation.

Table 1. Summary of policy stakeholder views

Change in practice by farmer or agricultural support industry	Policy interventions to facilitate changes
<p>Improve our capacity to diagnose situations where deep rooting is desirable and mobilise soil and crop management which support deep rooting</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Promote research and strengthen research facilities to understand the unfolding of the deep root phenotype, in its genetics, physiological and ecophysiological dimensions. › Promote research to optimise novel/alternative management practices (genotype mixtures, cropping associations, soil management, crop rotations) to improve root growth and resource capture. › Develop our capacity to diagnose and simulate, at the field, farm and regional scales, where and when deep rooting will turn into improve crop performance
<p>Develop varieties with increased deep rooting capacity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Identify optimal cultivars of crop species for optimal rooting at a local scale. This could be facilitated by increased funding for research and development in breeding › Promote research and strengthen research facilities to develop fast screening and evaluation methods to incorporate deep rooting in crop improvement criteria. › Sensibilize organisations responsible for cultivar evaluation at the regional scale to the importance of soil-root processes
<p>Develop farmers' awareness of the contribution of deep rooting and the management options to improve it</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Promote research at the interface of agronomy and social sciences on the adoption of innovations by farmers. › Promote the use of agricultural geomatics combining digital soil maps, Earth Observation data and soil-crop models as decision and management tools at the regional and farm scales. › Promote role of advisors to promote the use of appropriate crop and soil management which improve rooting. Incentivisation through the EU Green deal and farm payment schemes could be used.

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